

Fig. 1. Esr spectrum of spin adduct $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\overset{\text{H}}{\underset{\text{CHOH.CHOH.CH}_2\text{OH}}{\text{C}}}-\overset{\text{O}}{\text{N}}-\text{C}(\text{OH})_2$ formed during the photo-oxidation of propane-1,2,3-triol.

or its aqueous solution was purged with dry nitrogen to remove oxygen for 10–15 min prior to photolysis at room temperature. The lamps used were high pressure point sources (100 and 200 W), the output of which was filtered through broad band interference filter ($\lambda > 380$ nm). Control experiments were also performed and no esr signals were obtained from the photolysis of spin-traps under the experimental conditions in the absence of uranyl nitrate.

PBN⁸ was used in the photo-oxidation reactions of ethane-1,2-diol, propane-1,3-diol and propane-1,2,3-triol, while SPBN¹², a water soluble spin-trap, was used with the aqueous solutions of adonitol and mannitol (1.0 mol dm⁻³).

Results and Discussion

Nitrones have been used as spin-traps because of their thermal and photochemical stability and the absorption bands in the ultraviolet region ($\lambda <$

300 nm). The spin adducts (1 and 2) formed in these photo-oxidation reactions gave the typical esr spectra consisting of triplet (due to ¹⁴N, $I=1$), of doublets (due to β -hydrogen, $I=1/2$) (Fig. 1).

1 (Spin adduct of PBN) 2 (Spin adduct of SPBN)
R = Trapped radical

The splitting parameters for the different spin adducts formed in these reactions are given in Table 1.

The magnitudes of the esr parameters (Table 1) suggest the formation of carbon-centered free radicals in these photoredox reactions⁷⁻¹⁴. Two alternative mechanisms were proposed on the basis of the results of the liquid phase esr spin-trapping

TABLE 1—HYPERFINE SPLITTING CONSTANTS OF THE SPIN ADDUCTS FORMED DURING PHOTOLYSIS OF URANYL NITRATE IN PURE DIOLS, TRIOLS AND AQUEOUS ALDITOLS MEDIA

Substrate	Spin-trap	Radical (R)	a_N (mT)	$a_{\beta-H}$ (mT)	g _{av}
Ethane-1,2-diol	PBN	$\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH.CH}_2\text{OH}$	1.58	0.34	2.0056
Propane-1,3-diol	PBN	$\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH.CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	1.58	0.35	2.0060
Propane-1,2,3-triol	PBN	$\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH.CHOH.CH}_2\text{OH}$	1.56	0.34	2.0058
Adonitol	SPBN	$\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}(\text{CHOH})_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	1.60	0.38	2.0059
Mannitol	SPBN	$\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}(\text{CHOH})_3\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$	1.55	0.38	2.0061

studies of the photo-oxidation of monohydric alcohols by the uranyl ions^{7,8} and other metal ions⁹⁻¹². One is the hydrogen atom abstraction producing a carbon-centered hydroxyalkyl radical (equation 2) and the other the electron transfer reaction producing an oxygen-centered alkoxy radical (equations 3 and 4).

H-abstraction :

Electron transfer :

The results (Table 1 and Fig. 1) indicate that the evidence of spin-trapping of the carbon-centered radicals by the spin-trap (equation 5) supports the mechanism (equation 2) for the title reaction under the present experimental conditions.

where, R is the remaining part of the diol/triol/alditol molecule.

The hydrogen abstraction mechanism (equation 2) and the trapping of carbon-centered free radicals in these reactions are further supported by the matrix isolation experiment performed at 77 K using liquid nitrogen. The resulting esr spectrum obtained on the photolysis of uranyl nitrate (1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) in ethane-1,2-diol gave a familiar recognisable triplet ($a_H = 1.98$ mT) due to $\dot{\text{C}}\text{HOH}.\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ consistent with the earlier report¹⁴.

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Synthesis and Pharmacological Studies of 2-N-Ethyl-3,4-naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan

PRAMILA JAIN and B. C. JOSHI*

Chemical Laboratories, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004 and

F. S. K. BARAR

Department of Pharmacology, S. M. S. Medical College, Jaipur

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DETAILED studies of 6,7-benzomorphan¹, the potent analgesics with minor toxic effects², have resulted in the synthesis of various related compounds for the first time in our laboratory³. The modification of piperidine ring of 6,7-benzomorphan to benzo[*f*]tetrahydroquinoline system has resulted in 3,4-naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan which are of potential analgesic interest, 2-N-methyl-3,4-naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan is found to be toxic (ALD₅₀ = 273 mg/kg i.p.) with a significant analgesic ($P < 0.001$) and CNS depressant activity ($P < 0.001$).

The present communication deals with⁴ the synthesis and pharmacological evaluation of 2-N-ethyl-3,4-naphtho-6,7-benzomorphan (2) HCl. The structure was established by elemental analysis, ¹H nmr and mass spectral data.

In the ¹H nmr spectrum of 2.HCl (C₂₃H₂₁N.HCl), signals at δ 4.75 (2H, q) and 1.0 (3H, t) indicated the presence of N-ethyl group. Signals at δ 3.25 (2H, t) and 4.0 (2H, d) respectively accounted for methylene protons at C-8 and C-9. Signals at